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Startup Garage: The Way to Apply Knowledge

Check your idea. Get involved. Be inspired

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ABSTRACT

Based on the vocational model - which made Switzerland one of the best places for young people to start working - DTI *Startup Garage's* mission is to go further in developing individual skills, such as entrepreneurial attitude. At the end of October students are called to register their own business ideas. These will then be processed through an innovative web application (*PingelApp*), used to match proposal ideas with the most suited teacher and researcher, who have initially accepted to be *Standby Mentor*. Once associated with the student (*Idea Owner*), *Standby Mentors* assess the idea and, together with a larger evaluation committee, choose which student can be called *Idea Startupper*. *Standby Mentors* can voluntarily endorse the students' idea to be actively further supported. At the end of every academic year, *Idea Startupper*s who want to remain in the *Startup Garage* must pass through a tailor-made training program. The *Startupper* is responsible to develop her/his roadmap of technical and entrepreneurial knowledge. Room 177, aka *Startup Garage*, is organized exclusively to let students work at their ideas in a free area, now generally considered an enjoyable and creative place to be in.

1 INTRODUCTION

Based on the dual education system - which made Switzerland leader in Innovation (*Table 1*) and an outstanding country enhancing "Human capital" (see World Economic Forum: <https://www.weforum.org/reports/the-global-human-capital-report-2017>, consulted 2019/06/25) - DTI *Startup Garage's* mission is to go further in developing individual skills, such as entrepreneurial attitude, as the basis for students to possibly become entrepreneurs. To that effect, a method was developed to scout entrepreneurial ideas among all students who attend academic courses in different branches of the Department of Innovative Technologies (DTI) of the University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Southern Switzerland.

In order to contribute to keeping up the Swiss innovation ecosystem, a new concept has been developed in a Swiss university where experience is *leitmotiv* of the educational framework. "*Startup Garage Concept*" must be thought as a method-based search for applying knowledge aiming at discovering practical solutions. Problems are identified by students and, thanks to their creativity, bound to be solved in some way. In so doing, principles for promoting innovation are experienced by students attending courses at our university.

Startup Garage offers all students opportunities to turn knowledge into promising business ideas. Along those lines our motto is "The way to apply knowledge". The

way leading to *Startup Garage* is easier to engineering students, who are typically provided with natural talent useful to develop entrepreneurial skills. This kind of students have ideas and can turn them into action developing entrepreneurial spirit at the same time. In a way to discover ideas the team of *Startup Garage* carries out a horizontal approach and cross curricular scouting throughout all engineering bachelors.

Table 1. Bloomberg Innovation index, 2018 (from <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2019-01-22/germany-nearly-catches-korea-as-innovation-champ-u-s-rebounds>, consulted 2019/04/16)

2018 rank	2017 rank	YoY change	Economy	Total score	R&D intensity	Manufacturing value-added	High-tech Productivity	Tertiary density	Tertiary efficiency	Researcher concentration	Patent activity
1	1	0	S. Korea	89.28	2	2	21	4	3	4	1
2	2	0	Sweden	84.70	4	11	5	7	18	5	8
3	6	+3	Singapore	83.05	15	5	12	21	1	7	12
4	3	-1	Germany	82.53	9	4	17	3	28	19	7
5	4	-1	Switzerland	82.34	7	7	8	9	11	17	17
6	7	+1	Japan	81.91	3	6	24	8	34	10	3
7	5	-2	Finland	81.46	8	16	10	13	19	6	4
8	8	0	Denmark	81.28	6	15	11	15	26	2	10
9	11	+2	France	80.75	12	35	14	2	10	21	9
10	10	0	Israel	80.64	1	27	9	5	41	1	19
11	9	-2	U.S.	80.42	10	23	6	1	42	20	2
12	12	0	Austria	79.12	5	8	15	26	12	12	5
13	16	+3	Ireland	77.87	22	1	1	18	20	14	33
14	13	-1	Belgium	77.12	11	22	13	10	37	13	21
15	14	-1	Norway	76.76	19	37	19	11	23	8	14

A dynamic environment enables innovation to be promoted. Space and support to succeed are provided to innovative projects. A new kind of teaching method can identify good ideas among students with outstanding pioneering potential.

The main goal is to transfer knowledge gained by students at school and apply it by working at their own entrepreneurial ideas. The expectation is that the chances to set up and develop science-based companies will increase and science-based innovation will be encouraged. In promoting science-based entrepreneurial initiatives, connections between higher education institutions, the private sector, and society will be strengthened, and accelerated also through the use of digital tools [1].

2 GENERAL DESCRIPTION OF THE DTI STARTUP GARAGE

The main details of how it is working are:

- Students attend courses for a variety of bachelor studies, thus enabling useful cross-fertilization
- Active Standby Mentors are available to help students to develop their Startup ideas
- A webapp, PingelApp, associates the idea with the competent Standby Mentors
- Idea Startupperes can ask for financial support to develop their MVP (Minimum Viable Product) and obtain refunds for costs incurred in developing business ideas
- The Startup Garage Team is always available whenever students ask for assistance

- Lunch Seminars are organized to achieve milestones which mark progress in developing Startup Ideas and, if achieved, enable students to remain in the Startup Garage
- Business Cake Events with teachers and students are enjoyable moments to deepen discussions
- Assignment of vocational credits from courses teaching entrepreneurial soft skills, in order to integrate part of the courses taught by Standby Mentors
- Students can prepare their work in order to participate in competitions for the most prestigious startup accelerator
- Students promote their entrepreneurial ideas among secondary school pupils in order to foster innovation and creativity
- The Startup Garage offers entrepreneurship-related courses to students on an on-going basis

3 STARTUP GARAGE: A THREEFOLD CONCEPT

3.1 Startup Garage: the space where ideas can be worked on

Like an “island of freedom” (the name of the app comes from a Micronesia island: Pingelap) Room 177 at SUPSI, is a physical location of the *DTI Startup Garage*. Here, students can put classical theoretical-scientific instruments and knowledge, which they gradually obtain during their curricula, at work into a stimulating practical adventure. In fact, students are enabled to develop their own entrepreneurial ideas without taking the risks of real entrepreneurs, but growing into dynamic people enabled to become real entrepreneurs at the end of their academic path.

Startup Garage is an enjoyable and creative place set up recently inside a Department (DTI) that is focusing on the applied engineering sciences, in general within the industrial sector, and with technology and information services for both training and research.

In developing the “*Startup Garage Concept*”, a physical area had to be laid out, in order to make an impacting space useful to reach the main goals of the course. In the traditional conceptual framework, academic rooms are still thought as an orderly learning space where students can develop their ideas [2]. However, in Room 177, a new space has been created in which rules of freedom and openness help ideas to become useful products or services.

Only enrolled and motivated students, with good entrepreneurial ideas, obtain exclusive access to the *Startup Garage* and to its benefits. In the Garage students can put classical theoretical-scientific instruments and knowledge, which they gradually obtain during their curricula, into a stimulating practical adventure. But no credits are awarded yet, no award-winning contest is directly promoted, nevertheless *Idea Startupper*s are helped to take part in national and international related competition. Startup Garage is a methodological way to back vocational education and training as developed in Switzerland, in order to be much oriented towards entrepreneurship and self-consciousness of own business ideas.

3.2 An entrepreneurial approach to teaching: Teachers and Technology as supporters and facilitators

In a responsible way, engineering students, as motor and genius, are able to switch on a renewable digital economy boosted by freedom and creativity (*Fig. 1*). Leonardo Da Vinci, genius but “*omo senza lettere*”, put the **Man at the centre of the earth and**

universe. Accordingly, we should nowadays find next generation innovators, who put their good ideas at mankind's disposal.

Academic education, as delivery of learning, surely contributes to form and reshape breeding ideas, but it fails to promote entrepreneurial attitude, especially at the very beginning of the academic curricula.

Fig. 1. Student-centered approach - Personal elaboration

Beyond formal learning objectives, the management team of the *Startup Garage* is helping students to develop entrepreneurial ideas and go further into business aspects. Inside the Garage, students can find an openness and free access to functional knowledge to be tapped into in order to spread the entrepreneurial spirit among students.

This approach fosters collaborative creativity, sustainable adaptive learning, new credentialing, peer learning, and the understanding of assessing business opportunities on a continuous basis.

Management mission

The Startup Garage Team is made up of persons with different backgrounds but united by the same goal: helping students to succeed in their entrepreneurial initiatives as a good way to keep on studying in a stimulated academic environment.

In developing a particular entrepreneurial teaching approach (see “on a renewed EU agenda for higher education” <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52017DC0247>), the Team believes in human relationship as well as human capability to learn by doing, which has shown to be very useful to motivated students.

PingelApp

At *Startup Garage*, in order to support the entrepreneurial teaching aims, a collaboration started with ICT colleagues to exploit digital technologies for developing student business ideas and facilitating the management process. The initial approach was to develop a web application, *PingelApp*, that provided on one hand the capture, collection, and management of young students' ideas in a rationale and homogeneous way, and, on the other hand, it allowed a gathering of skills of potential teachers and researchers who could act as Standby Mentors. In this way students' idea needs and mentors' expertise are collected. A further step in this innovative platform for the management of ideas and of the ideation process was completed by

an algorithm that associates an idea with a potential mentor, based on the needs expressed in the idea description and the competences declared by the mentors.

The *PingelApp* project was developed in two phases: in the first phase, as a result of a semester project of the SUPSI Bachelor course in Computer Engineering [3], a first robust platform was created for the collection of ideas and skills, with a basic automatic matching mechanism mentor-idea; in a second phase, through a diploma thesis [4], the system was improved focusing on the graphical and algorithmic aspects of the application, in order to further facilitate the process of collecting and managing ideas thanks to a more usable and attractive layout, and at the same time, to find a better matching between mentors and ideas.

The heart of the webapp, i.e. the matching algorithm, was also enhanced thanks to the semantic relatedness similarity [5] between words of the WS4J library [6] based on WordNet [7]. Using the Wu/Palmer [8], Lin [9] and Lesk [10] algorithms, and the WordNet lexical database, the application currently calculates the correlation between ideas and Standby Mentor.

The development of this web application is still in progress both for what concerns the introduction of new functionalities and for the code cleaning and refactoring.

PingelApp Roles and Actors

The main features of the *PingelApp* can be summarized by describing the roles of the main actors involved.

Unauthenticated users can access all the published public information about ideas and calls on the web application. In addition, there are four main authenticated roles of users within the webapp: the *student*, the *standby-mentor*, the *manager*, and the *admin*.

Users with *manager* role can create, open and manage new calls for ideas, mainly by setting a title, a start and an end date. The manager can also define some visibility criteria to let other users access the presentation of ideas.

Standby-mentors can enter the system and, after having filled in their list of core-competencies to describe their expertise, find any associated idea, which matches the offered competences.

Users with *student* role act as idea owners, they can insert a new idea related to an open call for ideas, edit or view her/his inserted ideas, where the associated mentors are also displayed when available.

An *admin* user is also present in order to manage *PingelApp*, i.e. the creation, updating and deletion of all its elements.

Ideas are inserted according to a precise structure defined also on the basis of previous work carried out at SUPSI about a web application for managing the breeding of ideas [11].

The idea structure is a core concept at the base of *PingelApp* and is exploited to capture the essence of an idea through a number of fields: a title, a description, a representative image, an optional short video (such as a pitch), a story about the birth of the idea, differentiation, motivation, application fields, and required competencies.

An example (*Fig. 2*) in which an idea (left column) called SMARS — Screwless Modular Robotic System — has been associated by the *PingelApp* to a *Standby Mentor* who wanted to be active (self-candidates, right column), although the matching system recognized other possible *Standby Mentors* (suitable mentors proposed by the matching algorithm, central column).

Independently from the automatic *PingelApp* matching suggestion, *Idea Startupper*s do choose their favourite “Active Standby Mentor”. Throughout the entire matching

process the *Startup Garage Management* acts as supervisor and checks the consistency between the business idea and the Standby Mentor selected.

Active Standby Mentor: **Michele Banfi**

Possible Standby Mentor: Andrea Galli

Fig. 2. WebApp’s partial view of the matching between Ideas and Standby Mentors.

Idea Featuring

Business ideas are classified according to typical industry sector definitions as appeared in “Industry Classification Benchmark” published by the FTSE (<https://www.ftserussell.com/data/industry-classification-benchmark-icb>) and their *Supersector*, *Sector* and *Subsector*, where possible.

Assessment Process

Members of the *Startup Garage Management*, and *Standby Mentors* build-up the “Evaluation Committee” in charge of assessing entrepreneurial ideas to be eventually elected as *Startup Ideas*. Quantitative results are generated automatically in order to make this important task easier. Each *Standby Mentor* associated by the *PingelApp* to a particular idea receives the following “Assessment Sheet” (Fig. 3) to be filled out on the idea associated with him or her.

Name of the Startup Idea: @ Coffee

Evaluation criteria for admission to the DTI Startup Garage

Meaning of numerical evaluation:

- 1 = No Relevance
- 2 = Unforeseen Evaluation
- 3 = Some Chances If
- 4 = Good Opportunities
- 5 = Brilliant Future Applications

Put your numeral evaluation as defined above for each criteria listed in the table below

Innovation items	Technology Feasibility/Implementation	Potential Breakthroughs	Points

Name of the Standby Mentors assessing the Startup Idea: _____

NB: Admission is not granted if the results is below 6 points

Fig. 3. Idea's Assessment Sheet.

Once the presumably best ideas have been selected, “Idea Owners” will become “Idea Startupper”. They get a *Startupper kit*, made up of a T-shirt, a badge for 24h free access to the Startup Garage space and the opportunity to be assisted by an “Active Standby Mentor” who endorses the idea he or she has reviewed and

considered viable. As a result, *Active Standby Mentors* are ready to assist *Idea Startups* in progressing with their business ideas during their academic and vocational path, well beyond a particular semester period.

At the end of the academic year, the “Evaluation Committee”, based on an *add-on endorsement* by the *Active Standby Mentor*, decides if the project deserves to be further supported and if the team can maintain their status as *Idea Startups*.

3.3 Vocational Training Education

Entrepreneurship education is underpinned by the model depicted in *Fig. 4*. In order to carry out updating assessments, three milestones have been set to enable the evaluation progress on a regular basis. According to the contents of the milestones shown below, *Idea Startups* are invited to show what they have done in the previous 3 months and to explain the current status of their *Startup Idea*, inside an entrepreneurship education framework and training opportunities.

Fig. 4. Business Idea Management.

Functional Events

The Startup Garage Team organizes training units on general interest topics for entrepreneurial, personal and managerial skills with guest speaker or case studies.

Business cake events are organized every first Thursday of each month, special courses (often as lunch seminars) are offered to the *Idea Startups* comprising subjects such as “Teamwork”, “Business model, Business plan, Accounting and Financial sheets”, “Private funds from banks and business angels”, “Marketing”, “Intellectual property”, “Reports and presentations”, “Crowdfunding” bringing into focus Pitching tailored to enable the Startups to participate at important Swiss startup competitions.

Whilst the topics related to the technical, scientific and productive aspects linked to the idea are developed with the support of the *Standby Mentors* and with experts and entrepreneurs.

Soft Skills

The Startup Garage Team takes care of the application of soft skills [12] that allow *Idea Startuppers* to improve their own personal skills. The Startup Garage Team supports and motivates *Idea Startuppers* to overcome difficult times and situations with the aim of giving the skills so that the *Idea Startuppers* learn to support each other. In this sense, a focal point is the “Cross functionality”. Functional team members serve not only as the team’s conscience in their particular area of expertise, but also as enthusiastic ambassadors.”

4 STARTUPGARAGE, A USEFUL TOOL TO BUSINESS COMMUNITY

Startup Garage Team wants to foster willingness among students to put themselves into the foreground [13], to give some chances to their entrepreneurial ideas, and trim them to possibly go further in developing a real startup. We want to nourish Accelerators in a way to limit failures – not the right team, wrong business model, product not a hit, no market need, ... [14] and to increase the chances for achieving success. Most of the startups growing inside the academic environment have more chance to survive three years after being set up [15]. That is why we want to make the “culture of failure”, as promoted in the Silicon Valley, less traumatic than the virtue of becoming an entrepreneur.

We want to transform weaknesses into strengths in terms of spreading the word, continuing to look for students with good ideas so our “base” of entrepreneurial students becomes bigger. This will obviously increase the odds of having a real working company in the future.

5 FACT AND FIGURES

The balance of the first two years (*Table 2*) is certainly positive, all numbers are growing.

Table 2. Results 2018 and 2019

	1 st Edition 2017-2018	2 nd Edition 2018-2019	Increase
Ideas presented	11	17	+ 55%
Ideas accepted	7	13	+ 54%
Idea Startuppers	13	20	+ 77%
Standby Mentors	13	39	+300%

The *Idea Startuppers* transmit their positive experience to schoolmates; this “cross-fertilization” does not only involve young people, but also extends to teachers and researchers, companies, partners and experts.

6 FUTURE DEVELOPMENT

- Starting in 2021, the new Campus opens to all SUPSI Departments and to USI (one of the 12 certified public universities in Switzerland: <https://www.usi.ch/en>). The Startup Garage will then be transferred to the new Campus.
- Create and improve contacts with other Universities in Switzerland, in Europe and in China.
- Offer internships to *Idea Startuppers* in Departments that could offer added value to the development of the "working" business idea.

- Establish contacts with local companies that relate to the ideas of *Idea Startupper*s to offer summer work experience.
- Allow students of each Department for the possibility of being part of an *Idea Startupper*s Team by offering their scientific and technical knowledge.
- Provide ECTS credits for the skills acquired in the implementation phases expected to go further in developing Startup ideas.
- Let *Idea Startupper*s who finished their vocational experience in the Garage to become acquainted to the newly established Association “Friends of Startup Garage”.
- Making PingelApp available to other communities and improving the quality of the code for an open-source release.

7 CONCLUSION

The Startup Garage Concept it to be understood as a means to connect students to the entrepreneurship reality, despite the fact that they should remain on the path to their main goal: graduation.

A new educational space focused on the interaction between students, teachers and researchers who together create a multidisciplinary and tailor-made training laboratory to develop entrepreneurial ideas aimed at growing the local economy.

Startup Garage Method seeks to motivate students to look for a better future. Standby Mentors are involved in understanding entrepreneurship by helping *Idea Startupper*s and stimulated on finding new inspiring teaching and, why not, developing their own entrepreneurship attitude thank to dynamic students. Entrepreneurial student education therefore fits into a broader engineering curriculum and helps to manage the students career path, possibly the best way to match today’s needs of the job market.

In doing things real, a particular importance is given to partnerships with the business community, which is sharing their experience with students enabling them to put good ideas and entrepreneurial skills into practice.

Globalization speeds up the race to a common market in which a greater inclusion of diversity has to be ruled by a creative thinking and idea scouting, which in turn are sustained and strengthened by cross fertilization. Inter- and multidisciplinary is promoted by applying the “Startup Garage Concept” hence making room for an entrepreneurial approach to teaching.

Connecting the dots... to ensure that step by step
*Idea Startupper*s develop entrepreneurial and personal skills.

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